

Supporting Information

A Versatile Luminescent Ga-Organic Framework with Multi-emission Centers as a Blue LED and Fluorescent Probe for Low-temperature Detection and Selective Fe³⁺ Sensing

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1. Materials and Methods.

All reagents and solvents were purchased from commercial sources without further purification. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern was collected by a Rigaku MiniFlex600 diffractometer with Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$, 40 kV, 15 mA) at room temperature by 0.02 $^\circ$ steps. FT-IR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Tensor 27 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} . The UV-vis absorption spectra measured on a Hitachi U-3900 UV/vis spectrophotometer at room temperature. The temperature-dependent luminescent measurements were recorded a Horiba FluoroMax+ spectrofluorometer. The solid-state photoluminescence properties and metal ions sensing were recorded on Hitachi F-7100 fluorescence spectrophotometer at room temperature.

Figure S1. FT-IR spectra of the organic ligand and SNNU-63.

Figure S2. Excitation and emission spectra of the free H₃PTC ligand.

Figure S3. Excitation and emission spectra of SNNU-63.

Figure S4. The solid-state UV-Vis absorption spectra of SNNU-63 and the free H_3PTC ligand at room temperature.

Figure S5. The corresponding CIE 1931 chromaticity diagram of SNNU-63 at room temperature.

(a)

(b)

Figure S6. Comparison of photo for SNNU-63 under the natural light (a) and UV 254 nm light (b).

Figure S7. Excitation and emission spectra of SNNU-63 MOF aqueous suspension.

Figure S8. Luminescence intensity ($I_{382 \text{ nm}}$) of SNNU-63 to different metal ions in aqueous (0.4 mM) under excitation of 288 nm.

Figure S9. Fluorescence quenching of SNNU-63 dispersed in aqueous solutions of twelve different metal cations (0.4 mM).

Figure S10. Linearity relationship of luminescent intensity of SNNU-63 and Fe³⁺ ion at low concentrations.

Figure S11. The reversibility and recyclability of SNNU-63 dispersed in water in the presence of 0.4 mM aqueous solution of Fe^{3+} ions.